

Neural Networks for the Design and Fabrication of Integrated Circuits for Aerospace Applications

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION
2. ANN MODELING
3. IC PROCESS/DEVICE MODELING
4. EM-CAD MODELS
5. CONCLUSIONS

1. INTRODUCTION

The insertion of MIMIC components into aerospace sensor systems has helped reduce the size, weight, and cost of these systems while increasing performance. However, the ever increasing complexity of modern and future systems places an even greater demand on this technology. The non-recurring engineering cost associated with the MIMIC design and manufacturing process are still too high. Current practices typically involve several design, fabrication, and test cycles. Improvements to the CAE tools to achieve rapid and efficient designs are key to reducing these costs.

For MIMIC design the effectiveness of modern CAE methods relies on accurate models of active and passive circuit elements. For commonly used structures a great variety of models are available. However, as circuit

Abstract—A great effort has been underway in recent years to develop microwave and millimeter wave monolithic integrated circuit (MIMIC) technology for phased array radar systems for airborne and space based applications. Solid-state MIMICs have made a dramatic impact on capability, reliability, and cost of these sensor systems. However, the computer-aided engineering (CAE) tools necessary for the modeling and simulation of such complex systems has not kept pace. This paper presents a methodology for the utilization of neurocomputing technology to achieve enhanced yield and efficient yield prediction in integrated circuit (IC) manufacturing. Specifically, artificial neural networks (ANNs) are employed to model complex relationships between material and device characteristics at critical stages of the semiconductor fabrication process. Additionally, a methodology for the development of ANN models of MIMIC passive elements based on the elements physical parameters is described. Results are presented which illustrate that a ANN can predict the equivalent circuit parameters (ECPs) and/or the scattering-parameters of these passive elements to nearly the same degree of accuracy as that afforded by electromagnetic (EM) simulation.

densities and operating frequencies increase, the accuracy of conventional modeling techniques become questionable and are quite time consuming and labor intensive. Poor models result in inaccurate simulations and lead directly to increased hardware iterations and reduced performance. Variations in processes and the use of state-of-the-art technologies render many models useless. As performance requirements expand, the cost of the development and validation of advanced models defeat the cost effectiveness of microwave/millimeter wave CAD. Also, as the trend toward mixed-mode and multi-function MIMICs continues the need for a paradigm shift in the way models are developed and implemented is becoming ever more apparent.

Research on more accurate and efficient methods to model active and passive devices and the semiconductor manufacturing process has been pursued for decades. As new technologies begin to mature it is essential that they be transitioned into the development cycle of industrial systems. Artificial neural networks is one such intelligent computing technology that has matured to the point where insertion into the development cycle of such complex systems needs to be pursued.

In this paper, several applications of ANN models for the design and fabrication of MIMICs is presented. First, the development of neural network models for the estimation of IC parametric yield is demonstrated. Yield-limiting characteristics are modeled and the resulting value compared to acceptance windows to estimate the parametric yield. Secondly, neural network models are developed in the inverse direction. Device characteristics measured after the fabrication process is complete are used as the input to model critical in-process characteristics. The modeled characteristics are used for whole wafer mapping and statistical characterization.

Finally, an overview of a recent neural network approach for achieving fast and accurate CAD of high-frequency analog and microwave circuits is described. The approach enhances the ability to utilize electromagnetic analysis techniques in an interactive CAD environment. The modeling results are provided and compared to the actual measured values of each characteristic. An in-depth discussion of the results obtained in each application is presented.

2. ANN MODELING

Neurocomputing technologies have recently emerged as powerful modeling techniques. The reasons for a neural computation approach are numerous and are highlighted throughout this paper. Neural networks are known for the ability to encapsulate multidimensional statistical properties present in large data sets [1]. By examining the network during and after model development, complex cause-effect relationships between parameters become evident. Neurocomputing models are helpful in situations when analytical solutions are not practical to pursue due to the complexity of the physical models or relationships are not fully understood. Additionally, the ANN modeling approach is not limited to a specific technological area or process.

Neural network modeling techniques have been previously applied in such areas as microwave circuit analysis and optimization [2], microstrip circuit design [3], device characterization for VLSI simulation [4], and more recently via interconnect modeling [5].

The class of neural network and/or architecture selected for a particular model implementation is dependent on the problem to be solved. The class of ANN used in this modeling effort is the multilayer perceptron neural network or MLPNN. It has a feedforward architecture, as

shown in Figure 1, has one hidden layer, and uses continuous perceptrons. These networks have demonstrated the ability to perform complex nonlinear mappings, or identification of relationships, between input and output data through an adaptive weight connection matrix [6]. The MLPNN, among others, is well suited for the large database of measurements available for IC characterization.

The MLPNN models are developed using supervised training. The modeled parameters are extracted empirically. The network learns the mappings directly from instances of the input-output pairs in a training file. Training is facilitated through the application of the error back-propagation (BP) training algorithm. The BP algorithm, a gradient search technique, calculates the weight adjustment using the generalized delta learning rule. The algorithm used to implement the MLPNN was written in-house and is given in [7]. The size of the hidden layer in each MLPNN model was determined experimentally by varying the number of hidden neurons and selecting the number which resulted in the lowest training error over a number of training sessions. Each

model took 10-40 minutes to train on a 100 Mhz computer. Once trained, the recall of the modeled parameters from the network is almost instantaneous.

Upon completion of training, the resulting models were tested and evaluated. This included the evaluation of the network's ability to learn the mappings of the training data as well as its ability to generalize on the test set data. The testing technique used to evaluate the MLPNN's generalization capability is called cross-validation [8]. Cross-validation is a statistical technique in which the training sample and a validation sample are selected from the same population. The MLPNN is trained using the training sample. When the training error stops decreasing by an appreciable amount, the training is halted. The generalization capability of the network is then tested using the validation sample.

To quantify the modeling accuracy, the modeled values were compared to the actual measurements. In most cases the Person product-moment correlation, r , was calculated for each output as

Figure 1. MLPNN feedforward architecture.

$$r = \frac{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum (x_i - \bar{x})^2 \sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

where x_i is the measured value, y_i is the MLPNN computed value, \bar{x} is the measured sample mean, and \bar{y} is the MLPNN computed sample mean. The correlation coefficient indicates how well the modeled values match the actual values. A correlation coefficient near one indicates excellent predictive ability, while a coefficient near zero indicates little predictive ability. In addition, scatter plots of the MLPNN computed values versus the actual measured values were created to visually illustrate the modeling accuracy.

3. IC PROCESS/DEVICE MODELING

Integrated-circuit technologies are expected to produce uniform device properties over a large wafer area. This uniformity is difficult to achieve for Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) IC technology because of material and processing deviations. There are large variations, within a wafer, of important material properties which strongly influence yield-limiting factors in final device performance. In part, these material problems arise because of strong radial and axial variations in thermal gradients during bulk crystal growth, which affect local stoichiometry [9]. Other yield-limiting non-uniformities occur during the wafer fabrication process [10,11]. It is essential that these variations and the effects they have on device/circuit performance are understood and properly modeled.

Traditional IC process/device modeling approaches, whether analytical or empirical, do not utilize the parametric values specific to a certain device's location on a wafer. Variations of parametric values are typically represented statistically. Actually the values are random variables described by joint probability density functions [12,13]. Once the statistical distribution is determined, the effects of these variations on the device/circuits performance is analyzed by performing simulations by means of, among others, Monte Carlo techniques [14,15].

As shown in [9,16,17], many of these parametric variations do not occur in a random manner across a wafer but in a radial and/or axial pattern. Also, due to the physical correlations existing between FET characteristics these parameters should not be treated as uncorrelated, mutually independent random variables [18,19]. The modeling approach described in this paper presents a methodology in which a specific device's characteristics can be modeled based on its

physical location within a wafer. Correlated variations are represented in the characteristic values of each individual device.

In this section neural network models for the estimation of IC parametric yield are developed. Measurements of material and/or device characteristics taken at earlier fabrication stages are used to develop models of the final DC device parameters. Critical device characteristics are modeled and used to estimate the parametric yield. Neural network models are also developed in the inverse direction. Final device measurements are used as the input to model in-process characteristics. The modeled characteristics are used to provide insight into the uniformity of the fabrication process and is accomplished with minimal in-process testing.

Process/Device Characterization

IC manufacturing consists of many distinguishable fabrications stages. A large and representative number of measurements of process attributes, key device parameters, and layout geometries taken during the fabrication process is needed to provide a statistical database for neural network modeling. The classical method for obtaining the characteristics of semiconductor materials, processes, and devices is to collect data from microelectronic test structures.

The test data used in this work was taken across an entire wafer at a sufficient density to fully characterize the fabrication process and device variations across the wafer. The measurement data used for characterization originated from a 4x4.5 mm high-density test structure reticle repeated some 200 times on a 3" GaAs wafer. Each reticle contains an array of microelectronic test structures developed to analyze the uniformity of the fabrication process and the resulting device/circuit

performance characteristics. The majority of the characteristics were measured on the Metal Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor (MESFET) parametric test structure. This test structure/device (referred to as device from this point on) is at the center of this modeling effort.

Whole wafer testing was conducted on the starting substrate material (S) and during wafer processing at four critical steps: Ohmic or Post-contact (C), Post-recess (R), Post-gate (G), and at the completion of fabrication (Final or F). A discussion of the physical significance of each measured characteristic used in this modeling effort is beyond the scope of this paper. However, Table I, lists each characteristic by the fabrication stage which they characterize, name, and symbol. Parameters which characterize the same fabrication stage are grouped together and serve as input-output for each MLPNN model developed.

The characteristics were measured across the entire wafer in one test sweep. The parameter values are stored such that the reticle is identified by XXYY, and the structure within a reticle is identified with xxyy. Substrate characteristics, which are taken prior to the process step which defines the XXYY reticle location, are reported in millimeters. Computer routines have been written and verified that reference the millimeter data to the reticle locations. The measured characteristic is then assigned the respective reticle XXYYxxyy. This method of test structure identification allows for the tracking of parameter values for a specific device from one fabrication stage to the next. This is imperative to MLPNN model development. The characteristics for a specific device must be tracked from one stage to the next to maintain the input-output relationships necessary for creating training and modeling data sets. Also, the measured parameters

location within a wafer are maintained for the purpose of wafer mapping.

Data Selection

One of the principle objectives of this work is to model the effect that material and process variations have on the performance characteristics of the active devices used in integrated circuits. The active device is typically where the effects of these variations become most evident and is a major contributor to yield loss. Therefore, as mentioned earlier, the MESFET is at the center of this modeling effort. For network training purposes, a density of six data vectors per reticle was chosen. All measured parameters within a reticle are referenced to six specific XXYYxxyy MESFET locations. Training vectors are formed by assigning each of the non-MESFET characteristics to the nearest-neighbor MESFET. Training files were created for each of the fabrication process stages identified previously.

A training file consisting of data from each reticle would contain over 1200 training vectors. It is desirable to develop training files of a manageable size to train the neural network models in an efficient manner. Yet, one desires to have training files which statistically represent the variations across a wafer. Through the examination of the nature in which device variations occur [1,2], it was determined that a horizontal slice of reticles across the wafer would provide enough data to statistically characterize the wafer variations, yet provide a manageable data set.

Hence, a horizontal slice of 14 reticles across the middle of the wafer was chosen for training purposes, see Figure 2. This provided 84 data vectors. The data was analyzed and 15 data vectors, whose measurements indicated non-functional MESFETs (i.e. $I_{dss}=0$, etc.), were

TABLE 1

Material and MESFET Characteristics modeled using neural networks. Characteristics for each respective fabrication stage serve as input-output pairs for model development and verification.

Fabrication Stage	Characteristic Name	Symbol	Fabrication Stage	Characteristic Name	Symbol
S	2-Optical Scattering	OBSA/B	C	Drain-source sat. current	C-Idss
S	Neutral deep donor density	EL2	C	Drain-source resistance	C-Rds
S	Substrate resistivity	Rho	C	Contact resistance	Rc
S	Substrate Hall mobility	MuH	C	Contact metal sheet res.	C-Rsh
S	Substrate Carrier Conc.	Ns	C	Ohmic metal layer width	O-W
S	Doping Concentration	Nd	C	Ohmic metal sheet res.	O-Rsh
S	Implant Activation	ETA	R	Drain-source sat. current	R-Idss
S	Drift Mobility (Vg=0)	Mu0	R	Drain-source resistance	R-Rds
S	Drift Mobility (Vg=-1.5)	Mu1	F	Drain-source sat. current	F-Idss
G	Drain-source sat. current	G-Idss	F	Drain-source resistance	F-Rds
G	Drain-source resistance	G-Rds	F	Gate-source resistance	F-Rgs
G	Gate-source resistance	G-Rgs	F	Source resistance	F-Rs
G	Source resistance	G-Rs	F	Drain-gate resistance	F-Rdg
G	Drain-gate resistance	G-Rdg	F	Drain resistance	F-Rd
G	Drain resistance	G-Rd	F	Pinch-off voltage	F-Vpo
G	Pinch-off voltage	G-Vpo	F	Transconductance	F-Gm
G	Transconductance	G-Gm	G	Gate metal width	G-W
G	Gate metal sheet res.	G-Rsh			

S-Substrate/Active Layer, C-Ohmic/Post-Contact, R-Post-Recess, G-Post-Gate, F-final DC

discarded. Of the remaining 69 data sets, 50 were used to train the neural networks and 19 were reserved to test the neural networks. For testing the inverse models, data vectors of the

wafer's entire population of functional MESFETs, a total of 678, were used to perform whole wafer characterization of certain critical parameters.

Figure 2. Illustration of the horizontal cross-section across the wafer used for MLPNN modeling.

Yield Estimation

Accurate and computationally efficient methods for estimating integrated circuit parametric yield have been under development for years. In general, parametric yield is formulated by determining if the measured values of certain critical performance parameters fall within a predetermined tolerance range about the target value for that parameter. During IC fabrication, parametric test are performed to determine discrepancies between the actual performance and the desired performance. This can involve the screening of final, or F-stage, DC device parameters such as: saturated drain current, $F-I_{dss}$; transconductance, $F-G_m$; and pinch-off voltage, $F-V_{po}$. Accurate estimation of parametric yield during the manufacturing process relies on the ability to predict the effect of material and process

variations on device parameters. The MLPNN models accomplish this task.

MLPNN Models—Three models of the F-stage DC characteristics were developed, refer to Figure 3, each model having input which represents a different stage of the fabrication process. Specifically the three models are denoted as; 1) S->F, has 10 measurements used to characterize the substrate and active layer materials as input; 2) CR->F, has 8 measurements taken at the post-contact and post-recess stage as input; and 3) G->F, has 8 measurements made at post-gate as input. The characteristics for each respective stage are given in Table 1. The number of hidden layer perceptrons for each model was determined experimentally as 22.

Results—Upon completion of training, each test vector was used as input to the respective

MLPNN model. The three MLPNN models are used to predict all of the F-stage characteristics, for each of the 19 MESFETs in the test set. However, for predicting yield only the three most yield-limiting characteristics, F-Idss, F-Gm, and F-Vpo, were examined. The yield is estimated by comparing these modeled values to the tolerance ranges for the respective characteristic. If the value falls within the range then it is considered to have passed, if not it fails. The estimated percent yield is then calculated and compared to the actual yield. For a discussion on the MLPNN performance with respect to all F-stage characteristics refer to [20].

Figure 4a-c, are bar charts of the actual yield and estimated yield using each MLPNN model's predicted values of F-Idss, F-Gm, and F-Vpo. The yield is calculated for three tolerance ranges; $\pm 5\%$ (Fig. 4a), $\pm 10\%$ (Fig. 4b), and $\pm 20\%$ (Fig. 4c). The tolerance ranges are computed as $\pm 5\%$, 10% , and 20% of the parameters target values. The target value for each parameter is: Idss= 227 mA, Gm= 208 mS, and Vpo= -1.54 V.

Figure 3. The three different MLPNN models developed. Each model independently predicts the output parameters.

As can be seen from Figure 4, the MLPNN computed values resulted in yield estimates which are very accurate. However, as the tolerance range decreased (such as the 5% range) so does the accuracy of the estimated yield. Also, the yield estimates were better for the MLPNN models developed using characteristics measured at later stages of the fabrication process. The accuracy range went from very good for the S->F MLPNN to excellent for the CR->F and G->F MLPNNs. Even for the tight tolerance range of 5%, the yield estimates are very credible.

Inverse MLPNN Models

Developing methods to provide affordable and reproducible high frequency products is a major objective of the GaAs IC industry. Fundamental to meeting this objective is to increase circuit yields by developing uniform fabrication technologies. This requires the analysis and statistical characterization of critical process and device characteristics across many wafers. Ideally, this analysis would utilize whole wafer high density material, process, and device characteristics measured at critical stages of the fabrication process. A large number of measured characteristics, taken across many wafers, is needed to provide a statistical database for process and device characterization. The amount of testing required to obtain the data to implement the ideal approach is prohibitive. A dominant factor in the high cost associated with IC product development is testing requirements. Typically, whole wafer testing is only performed after fabrication is complete.

The inverse modeling approach described here presents a methodology in which whole wafer in-process characterization is possible with minimal in-process testing. This reduced testing makes it affordable to analyze the process and device variations over many

a)

b)

c)

Figure 4. Comparison of actual and MLPNN computed yield a) 5% b) 10% c) 20% Tolerance.

wafers. Thus, allowing one to examine the most crucial variations and the effect they have on IC performance.

MLPNN Models—All four critical stages of the GaAs MESFET IC fabrication process were selected for inverse modeling. That is, substrate/active layer (S), post-contact (C), post-recess (R), and post-gate (G). Figure 5 illustrates the four different process stage models developed. Each model has as input the same 8 F-stage characteristics listed in Table 1 and independently predicts the output characteristics of each respective fabrication stage. Due to the absence of whole wafer test data for some substrate/active layer characteristics and to improve model efficiency, the number of output characteristics for some of the inverse MLPNN models were slightly reduced from those listed in Table 1. Therefore, the symbol of the specific characteristics modeled for each stage are provided below. Refer to Table 1, for the names of the characteristics the symbols represent.

The four process stage models are denoted as: 1) F->S, which consists of 7 outputs. Best results during training were obtained using a hidden layer consisting of 17 perceptrons. The outputs of the F->S stage model are the characteristics of the bare substrate and the ion-implanted active layer: Nd, Ns, EL2, ETA, Rho, Mu0, MuH; 2) F->C, consists of 4 outputs. Best results during training were obtained using a hidden layer consisting of 12 perceptrons. The outputs of the F->C stage model are the post-contact characteristics: C-Idss, C-Rds, C-Rsh, O-Rsh; 3) F->R, consists of 2 outputs. Best results during training were obtained using a hidden layer consisting of 8 perceptrons. The outputs of the F->R stage model are the post-recess characteristics: R-Idss, R-Rds; 4) F->G, consists of 9 outputs. Best results during

training were obtained using a hidden layer of 19 perceptrons. The outputs of the F->G stage model are the post-gate characteristic: G-Idss, G-Rds, G-Vpo, G-Rd, G-Rgs, G-Gm, G-Rs, G-Rdg, G-Rsh.

Results—Table 2, lists the statistical mean and standard deviation for the modeled values and the actual measurements for each characteristic modeled using the F->C, F->R, and F->G MLPNNs. The statistics were taken over the 678 test sets. The statistics of the MLPNN predicted values are in excellent agreement with the actual statistics. Figure 6a is the wafer map of the measured G-Idss values, while Figure 6b is the wafer map of the MLPNN modeled G-Idss. As can be seen the general spatial relationship of the characteristic across the wafer are recreated. Figure 7a-b, shows the same relationship for the R-Idss characteristic.

A wafer map is a color/gray scale image of a selected parameter where the distribution of the characteristic values is divided into sub-ranges represented by a particular shade. These mappings provide a visual representation of

Figure 5. The four inverse MLPNN models developed.

TABLE 2

Measured and modeled characteristics for inverse MLPNN models.

Characteristic	Actual Mean	Modeled Mean	Actual Std. Dev	Modeled Std. Dev
G_Idss	221	223	36.2	39.2
G-Rds	2.83	2.83	0.267	0.30
G-Rgs	3.79	3.78	0.152	0.137
G-Rs	1.10	1.08	0.058	0.054
G-Rdg	3.47	3.47	0.191	0.167
G-Rd	0.798	0.764	0.079	0.077
G-Vpo	-1.43	-1.47	0.217	0.243
G-Gm	204	208	7.37	7.66
G-Rsh	0.059	0.057	0.0024	0.0019
R-Idss	638	646	34.3	37.1
R-Rds	2.35	2.42	0.129	0.138
C-Idss	925	924	28.2	33.1
C-Rds	1.79	1.77	.075	.082
C-Rsh	1.63E4	1.64E4	750	1097
O-Rsh	0.349	0.335	.019	.019

how the parameters vary across a wafer. Observations can lead to design changes to compensate for uncontrollable material properties, and/or fabrication process changes can be made to eliminate undesirable process variations. Additionally, the amount of in-process testing required to train the MLPNN models is only 5% of the testing typically required to obtain these wafer maps. This represents a considerable cost savings.

Whole wafer comparisons are not available for the S-stage characteristics. This is due to the destructive nature of the test required for characterization.

4. EM-CAD MODELS

The high cost associated with the development of MIMIC circuits is due in part to the long design cycles and the number of design iterations to "get it right." As MIMICs become more compact to reduce the amount of area required for circuit layout, electrical proximity effects begin to dominate. Typical circuit

simulator supplied passive element models do not accurately account for the parasitic and coupling effects which occur at microwave/millimeter wave frequencies [21]. To remedy this situation, libraries of passive components have been developed by actually fabricating, testing, and storing the results of hundreds of elements [22]. This approach is problematic since the libraries are process dependent, costly to create, and limits the designer to a discrete set of components.

More recently, electromagnetic (EM) analysis tools have become commercially available which accurately model passive structures into the millimeter wave frequency range [23]. EM simulation effectively models dispersion and mutual coupling effects ignored by traditional circuit simulation tools. However, EM simulation methods, such as those in [24], take tremendous computational efforts and are not practical for interactive CAD.

In this section a methodology is described in which a MLPNN can be implemented to model

Figure 6. Wafer maps of the measured and modeled post-gate I_{dss} , G- I_{dss} .
 a) Measured. b) MLPNN Modeled

Figure 7. Wafer maps of the measured and modeled post-recess I_{dss} , R- I_{dss} .
 a) Measured. b) MLPNN Modeled

monolithic IC passive elements to nearly the same degree of accuracy as that afforded by EM simulation. The training data for model development was obtained by performing a full-wave electromagnetic analysis of these elements. To demonstrate this concept, two examples are provided. In the first example,

frequency independent π -network ECPs for 32 microstrip square spiral inductors are modeled. The inputs to the neural network model are the physical dimensions of the inductor (width, spacing, length, and number of turns), while the output is the ECPs for that inductor. In the second example, an X-band MLPNN spiral

inductor model is developed where the frequency dependent scattering parameters (s-parameters) of the inductors are modeled. Inputs to the neural network model are the physical dimensions of the inductor and the desired frequency point. The output is the s-parameters for that inductor at the respective frequency point.

The s-parameter model implementation is best suited for microwave design at frequencies above which the passive component response becomes strongly frequency dependent. The MLPNN computed s-parameter values are in excellent agreement with those obtained from EM simulations with correlations greater than 0.99 for all modeled parameters.

The strength of this approach is that only a minimum number of EM simulations on these passive elements are required to capture critical input-output relationships. Once trained, the computation time of the modeled parameters is negligible, which makes the MLPNN models suitable for interactive CAD applications. Furthermore, the MLPNN's ability to generalize may eliminate the need to always perform such time consuming EM simulations.

High Frequency EM-CAD Models

In this example the equivalent circuit model parameters for MMIC square spiral inductors are modeled. The ECP representation is best suited for high-frequency analog CAD applications at which the passive element response is not as frequency dependent. High-frequency simulators typically utilize these lumped element nodal models. The ECPs were extracted from full wave electromagnetic simulation results and are used to train a MLPNN. The MLPNN was trained using a data set consisting of the ECPs of 32 distinct square spiral inductors. The MLPNN computed ECP values are in excellent

agreement with the extracted ECPs. The MLPNN's ability to generalize the ECPs of inductors outside the training set is also demonstrated.

EM Simulation and Extraction—The π -network equivalent circuit representation, Figure 8, of the physical inductor is useful when designing high-frequency analog circuits, and is easy to incorporate in commercially available CAD tools. This simplified circuit is adequate for frequencies less than about two-thirds the resonant frequency for inductors fabricated using current monolithic integrated circuit technology.

Electromagnetic simulations of square spiral inductors were performed using *em* from Sonnet Software [25]. Scattering parameters for 32 inductors were obtained over a frequency range of 1 to 15 GHz at 1 GHz intervals. The physical dimensions of the inductors varied in width (10,15,20,25 μm), length (200,225,275,300 μm), spacing (10,15,20 μm), and number of turns (1.5,2.5). The dielectric and metalization were consistent among the inductors. π -network ECPs were then extracted for each inductor from the s-parameters.

The extraction process proceeded by first converting the s-parameters to admittance parameters (y-parameters). Then ECPs were readily computed from the following relations:

$$C_1 = \text{Im}\{y_{11}+y_{12}\}/w \quad (2)$$

$$C_2 = \text{Im}\{y_{22}+y_{21}\}/w \quad (3)$$

$$R = \text{Re}\{-1/y_{12}\} \quad (4)$$

$$L = \text{Im}\{-1/y_{12}\}/w \quad (5)$$

where C_1 and C_2 are the input and output capacitance, R is the series resistance, L is the series inductance, and w is the frequency in radians. $\text{Re}\{\}$ and $\text{Im}\{\}$ represent the real and imaginary parts of the argument.

Figure 8. Equivalent circuit π -network of inductor.

The ECPs were uniquely extracted at each frequency point and verified to be frequency independent. The frequency band of interest in this example is 1-7 GHz and this ECP model accurately represents the EM simulated behavior over this frequency range.

MLPNN Model—A block diagram of the MLPNN model is shown in Figure 9. The number of hidden layer perceptrons was experimentally determined as 16. The inputs to the model are the physical dimensions of the inductor and the resulting output represents the extracted ECP values. Training and test data vectors are created by forming an input-output pair for each inductor.

Figure 9. Block diagram of MLPNN model.

Results—First, the MLPNN was trained and tested using all 32 data vectors. This determines the network's ability to accurately learn the complex input-output mappings present in the data. The correlations between the extracted ECPs and the MLPNN computed ECPs were calculated using (1). The correlation coefficient, r , for each output parameter is given in Table 3. The MLPNN modeled parameters are extremely accurate as evidenced by the very high correlations. Figures 10a and b show scatter plots of extracted and modeled values for the two most important ECPs, resistance and inductance. These results exhibit minimum error and provide an excellent indication of the MLPNN's ability to capture the input-output relationships present in the data.

TABLE 3

Correlation coefficient between the extracted and MLPNN computed ECP values for all 32 inductors in example one.

ECP	C1	C2	R	L
r	.981	.982	.995	.999

Secondly, the same 32 data vectors were used to study the MLPNN's ability to generalize on the inductor data. The data set was shuffled, and 24 vectors were selected randomly for MLPNN training. The remaining 8 vectors were used to test network generalization. Tables 4a and b give the correlation coefficient between the extracted ECPs and MLPNN computed ECPs for the training and test data sets, respectively. As indicated in Table 4a, there is excellent agreement between the extracted and computed values for the 24 inductors in the training set. Referring to Table 4b, there is a noticeable drop in the correlation coefficients for the capacitance parameters (C1 and C2) for the test set; however, the correlations of the most important parameters

(R and L) remain high. This difference could be attributed to these capacitance's relatively small contribution to the admittance at the frequency range under study [22]. Although not shown here, the MLPNN computed ECPs for the test set inductors recreate the original s-parameters quite well. Figures 11a and b show scatter plots of extracted and modeled values for the test set inductance and resistance.

The purpose of the generalization study was simply to obtain some measure of the MLPNN's ability to generalize the data. The results indicate that the network may be capable of providing accurate generalizations. The authors are currently conducting a detailed design of experiments to establish the extent to which the MLPNN can generalize the inductor data.

TABLE 4

Correlation coefficients from the first example between the extracted and MLPNN computed ECP values for a) training set b) test set.

ECP	C1	C2	R	L
r	.983	.982	.997	.999

a)

ECP	C1	C2	R	L
r	.827	.744	.974	.988

b)

Microwave EM-CAD Models

The second example demonstrates the application of this technique for frequency dependent modeling. A MLPNN is trained to model the s-parameters of 32 distinct square spiral inductors at X-band, 7-11 GHz in 1 GHz steps. The s-parameters were obtained from full wave electromagnetic simulations. Also, the MLPNN's ability to generalize the s-

parameters of inductors outside the training set is demonstrated.

EM Simulations—The s-parameter data generated from the EM simulations for example one were also utilized in the second example. However, in example two, the s-parameters are modeled directly. Since the spiral inductor is a passive component the magnitude and phase of the forward transmission coefficient (S21) is equivalent to the magnitude and phase of the reverse transmission coefficient (S12). In this work, it was observed that the magnitude of the input reflection coefficient (S11) and the magnitude of the output reflection coefficient (S22) were also nearly equal. Therefore, only a reduced set of five s-parameters (MAG S11, ANG S11, MAG S21, ANG S21, and ANG S22) were used for MLPNN modeling and the subsequent comparisons between the EM simulated and MLPNN computed s-parameters.

MLPNN Model—A block diagram of the MLPNN model is shown in Figure 12. The input parameters for the model are the frequency and the inductor's physical dimensions. The resulting outputs represent the reduced set of simulated s-parameter values. Training and test data vectors are created by forming an input-output parameter pair for each inductor.

Results—As in the first example, a MLPNN was trained and tested using all 32 data vectors. This allows one to determine the network's ability to accurately learn the complex input-output mappings present in the data. The correlations between the EM simulated and the MLPNN computed s-parameters were computed as given by (1). The correlation coefficient, r, for each output parameter is given in Table 5. The MLPNN computed parameter values are extremely accurate with

Figure 10. Scatter plot of extracted and MLPNN computed parameters for all 32 inductors from the first example. a) R, resistance b) L, inductance.

Figure 11. Scatter plot of extracted and MLPNN computed parameters from the example one generalization test set. a) R, resistance b) L, inductance.

correlations approaching one. Figures 13a and b show scatter plots of EM simulated and MLPNN modeled values for the magnitude and angle of the forward transmission coefficient, MAG S21 and ANG S21, respectively. These

results exhibit minimum error and provide an excellent indication of the MLPNN's ability to capture the cause and effect relationships present in the data.

Figure 12. Block diagram of MLPNN model of example two.

To study network generalization the data set was examined, and 24 vectors were selected for MLPNN training. The remaining 8 vectors were used to test network generalization. Table 6 lists the correlation coefficient between the EM simulated s-parameters and the MLPNN computed s-parameters for the test data set. As indicated by the values of the resulting correlation coefficients, there is excellent agreement between the EM simulated and MLPNN computed values over the desired frequency. There exists a minimal decrease in r value between the training and test set of example two.

TABLE 5

Correlation coefficient between the EM simulated and MLPNN computed s-parameter values for all 32 inductors in example two..

OUT PUT	MAG S11	ANG S11	MAG S21	ANG S21	ANG S22
r	.9903	.9995	.9924	.9997	.9999

Figures 14a and b show scatter plots of EM simulated and MLPNN computed values for the test set magnitude and angle of the forward transmission coefficient, MAG S21 and ANG

TABLE 6

Correlation coefficients from the second example between the EM simulated and MLPNN computed s-parameter values for the test set.

OUT PUT	MAG S11	ANG S11	MAG S21	ANG S21	ANG S22
r	.9925	.9927	.9916	.993	.994

S21, respectively. These results exhibit minimum error and provide an excellent indication of the MLPNN's ability to provide accurate generalizations.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents an approach in which a neural network is employed to model semiconductor process/device characteristics and monolithic IC passive elements. The modeling technique described utilizes the multilayer perceptron neural network. The methodology provides new capabilities, as well as, distinct advantages over conventional modeling techniques. Several examples are provided and data presented which indicate the technique can provide accurate results.

It is shown that the MLPNN is a useful tool for estimating the parametric yield during the manufacturing process. Using an inverse modeling approach, we have demonstrated the MLPNNs ability to provide whole wafer statistics and wafer maps of important characteristics at critical stages of the fabrication process. This is accomplished by utilizing just a small percentage of in-process testing. Each approach eliminates the need to statistically describe parametric variations across a wafer. Training is accomplished by using the actual measurements as input and output pairs. The MLPNN inherently encodes the statistics of these variations. The ANN

Figure 13. Scatter plot of EM simulated and MLPNN computed s-parameters for all 32 inductors from the second example a) MAG S21 b) ANG S21

Figure 14. Scatter plot of EM simulated and MLPNN computed parameters from the example two test set a) MAG S21 b) ANG S21.

approach is technology independent and can be extended to other fabrication processes.

Also, examples were provided which describe how the MLPNN can be employed for accurate

modeling of MIMIC passive elements for interactive CAD applications. In the first example, the MLPNN demonstrates the ability to compute ECPs nearly as accurate as those extracted from full wave EM simulation results.

In the second example, the MLPNN demonstrates the ability to compute frequency dependent s-parameters as accurate as those obtained directly from full wave electromagnetic simulations.

Once trained, the computation time required for the modeled parameters is negligible as compared to other techniques such as full wave EM. This computational speed makes the network suitable for interactive CAD applications. This approach demonstrates that the performance of passive elements can be accurately predicted without the need to develop costly model libraries. Although the two examples illustrated inductor passive element modeling, the methodology can be applied to most passive structures.

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